

ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA ADABIY TANQIDIY MAQOLALARNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada adabiyotshunoslik ilmida adabiy tanqidiy maqolalarning o'ri va ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritildi. Badiiy asarning estetik qirralarini aniqlash, badiiy asarda ilgari surilgan g'oyani belgilashda adabiy tanqidiy maqolaning o'ri tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqola, tanqid, estetika, estetik kategoriya, janrlar sistemasi, sotsialistik metod.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРНО-КРИТИЧЕСКИХ СТАТЕЙ В ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье обсуждались роль и значение литературно-критических статей в науке литературоведения. Проанализирована роль литературно-критической статьи в определении эстетических аспектов художественного произведения, определении идеи, выдвинутой в художественном произведении.

Ключевые слова: статья, критика, эстетика, эстетическая категория, система жанров, социалистический метод.

THE IMPORTANCE OF LITERARY CRITICISM ARTICLES IN LITERARY STUDIES

Abstract. In this article, the role and importance of literary critical articles in the science of literary studies was discussed. The role of a literary critical article in determining the aesthetic aspects of a work of art, defining the idea put forward in a work of art was analyzed.

Key words: article, criticism, aesthetics, aesthetic category, system of genres, socialist method.

Haqiqiy o'tmishimizni chuqur bilish, milliy iftixor tuyg'ularini o'stirish asosida, o'zligimizni yanada teran anglash uchun adabiy tanqidchilik haqida bahs yuritish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Zero, adabiy tanqid jamiyat va adabiyot hodisalarini haqqoniy baholash orqali xalqning ma'naviy saviyasini yuksaltirish, estetik didini tarbiyalab, komil insonni shakllantirishdek ezgu ishga katta yordam beradi.

Adabiy tanqid adabiyotshunoslikning asosiy sohalaridan biri hisoblanadi. "Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati"da adabiy tanqidga quyidagicha ta'rif berilgan. *Adabiy tanqid - arabcha "muhokama qilish", "saralash" degan ma'nolarni anglatadi. Adabiyotshunoslikning asosiy sohalaridan biri. Adabiy tanqid hozirgi adabiy jarayon muammolarini o'rganish, yangi paydo bo'lgan asarlarni bugungi kun nuqtayi nazaridan g'oyaviy-badiiy tahlil va talqin qilish, baholashni maqsad qilib qo'yadi.* [1, 10-12]

Adabiy tanqidning paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishida, avvalo, kitobxonning ijtimoiy estetik ehtiyojlari yetakchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan. Chunki biror-bir badiiy asarni o'qib chiqqan savodxon o'quvchida o'z fikr-mulohazalarini bayon etish, qolaversa, muallif bilan fikrlashish istagi paydo bo'ladi. Ana shu ma'naviy ehtiyoj davrlar o'tishi bilan adabiy tanqidchilikning yuzaga kelishiga, maxsus fan sifatida shakllanishiga sharoit tug'dirgan. Adabiy-tanqidiy asarlarda badiiy asarning yutuq va kamchiliklari, ijodkorning badiiy mahorati haqida ilmiy mulohaza

yuritilibgina qolmasdan, muayyan bir jamiyatning ijtimoiy manfaatlari ham aks etgan bo‘ladi va, umuman, bu soha qadimdan falsafa, estetika, etika fanlari bilan uzviy aloqadorlikda rivojlanib kelgan. Shuning uchun ham Epikur va Aristotel zamonidan boshlab, adabiy tanqidchiga faylasuf, tarixchi – siyosatshunos, huquqshunos, ruhshunos sifatida ham qarab kelingan. Xullas, tarixiy-adabiy manbalar “adabiyotshunoslik”, “adabiy tanqid”, “tanqidchi” atamallari, jahon adabiyoti va ilmiy tafakkuri taraqqiyotida ko‘p yillik tarixga ega.

Agar o‘zbek adabiyoti tarixiga nazar tashlasak, yigirmanchi asrgacha bo‘lgan davrlarda adabiyotshunoslik va adabiy-tanqidiy qarashlar zamonaviy tanqidchilikdan farqli tarzda mavjud bo‘lganini kuzatish mumkin. O‘tmishda adabiyotshunoslik va adabiy tanqid fan sifatida mustaqil bir yo‘nalishda bo‘lmagan. Shunday esa-da, bu soha qadim-qadimdan boshlab she‘riy shaklda tazkiralardan, adabiyotshunoslikka oid ba‘zi bir risolalardan, tarixiy-badiiy yodnomalardan o‘rin olib, rivojlanib kelgan. Ayniqsa, she‘r va she‘riyat ilmiga oid risolalar hamda tazkiralardagi adabiy-tanqidiy tafakkurga oid turli xil fikr va qarashlar mumtoz adabiyot taraqqiyotida muhim o‘rin tutgan.

Ta’kidlash joizki, Sharqda Navoiygacha va undan keyin ham adabiyotshunoslik bobida ko‘p xayrli ishlar qililib, bir talay asarlar yozilgan. She‘riyat nazariyasi va tanqidchiligiga oid fikr-mulohazalar o‘tmishda nafaqat tazkiralarda, balki Forobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Bobur kabi ma’naviyatimizning ulug‘ namoyandalari asarlarida ham keng ifoda etilganki, bu jihatdan ularning she‘r va shoirlik mas’uliyati haqidagi qarashlari adabiyotshunoslik, adabiy tanqid ilmining rivojiga sezilarli ta’sir etgan. Masalan, Forobiy she‘r san’ati va uning vazifasini shunday belgilaydi: “Bu san’at – biror maqsadni amalga oshirayotgan paytda, yo‘ldan chiqib ketmaslikka yordam beruvchi va inson xayolini qog‘ozda namoyon etuvchi san’atdir. She‘rning olti xili bor. Shundan uchta yaxshi va uchta yomondir. Yaxshilardan biri shuki, uning yordamida inson aqliy quvvatini mukammallashtiradi, saodatga olib boruvchi fikri oydinlashadi, yaxshi ishlarga, fazilatli bo‘lishga ilhomlanadi, xasislik, yomon va qabih ishlardan saqlanadi. Ikkinchi yaxshi xili kishining ruhiy sezgilarini yuksaltiradi, haddan tashqari ehtiyotkorlikdan xoli qiladi, izzat-nafsnini saqlaydi, g‘azablanishdan, yomon ishlardan ehtiyot qilishga yordam beradi. Uchinchi kishini zaiflikdan saqlaydi, uning nafsinini, hirsini tiyadi, g‘amdan xalos qiladi, yomonlik oldida ana shu yuqorida qayd qilingan ijobiy xislatlarni namoyon etishga yordam beradi”.

O‘zbekistonda adabiy-tanqidiy qarashlar va adabiyotshunoslik ilmining rivoji XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmidan yangicha tamoyillar kasb eta boshladi. Taniqli adabiyotshunos olim Baxtiyor Nazarovning ta’kidlashicha, XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmidagi o‘zbek matbuotiga, xususan, “Turkiston viloyatining gazetasi”ga nazar tashlansa, bugungi tushunchamizga o‘xshash xususiyatlarga ega bo‘lgan adabiy-tanqidiy maqolalarga duch kelish mumkin va, aynan, o‘sha davrdan boshlab tom ma’nodagi malakali tanqidchilikka asos solindi.

XX asr sho‘ro tanqidchiligi esa adabiy jarayon va yozuvchi erkiga zo‘rakilik bilan ta’sir o‘tkazishga moslashgan edi. Bu hol xatolarni keltirib chiqardi. Lekin kommunistik mafkuraviylik va davr siyosatidan qat’i nazar, adabiy tanqidning bosib o‘tgan og‘ir yo‘lida ma’lum ijodiy samaralar, jumladan, badiiy mahorat, ijodiy o‘ziga xoslikning xususiyatlarini ochib bergan tadqiqotlar yuzaga keldiki, ularni bugungi kunda har tomonlama o‘rganish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Izzat Sulton, Homil Yoqubov, Vohid Zohidov, G‘ulom Karimov, Matyoqub Qo‘shjonov, Aziz Qayumov, Ozod Sharafiddinov, Laziz Qayumov, Salohiddin Mamajonov, Umarali Normatov, Ibrohim G‘afurov, Nuriddin Shukurov, Sobir Mirvaliyev, Baxtiyor Nazarov, Norboy

Xudoyberganov singari tanqidchilar adabiy jarayonda yuz berayotgan hodisa va o'zgarishlarni o'zlarining maqolalari hamda ilmiy ishlarida umumlashtirdilar. Ularning adabiyotimizning tarixi, o'sha davrdagi adabiy jarayon haqidagi mulohazalari natajasida oltmishinchi-yetmishinchi yillar o'zbek adabiy tanqidchiligida uslubiy rang-baranglik, risolalar yaratish tanqidchining tarixiy-biografik yondashuvi borasida ma'lum muvaffaqiyatlarga erishildi.

XX asr tanqidchiligida o'zbek romani, qissachiligi, dramaturgiya, poema va hikoyachiligi kabi adabiy tur va janrlarning tarkib topishi hamda taraqqiyot bosqichlarini ham keng tahlil qiluvchi tanqidiy biografik tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilishi va ularning dunyoga kelishida jahon adabiy tanqidchiligining bu sohada qo'lga kiritgan yutuqlarining ta'siri sezilarli bo'ldi.

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